

Appendix

A.1 Test results and training data per participant

Participant:	Amount of Earcons with FS* chosen:	Amount of Earcons without FS* chosen:	Amount of unmapped Earcons chosen:	Days between test and training:	Musical background:	Total amount of encounters of all hashtags during training:
1	4	4	4	6	No	28
2	8	3	1	4	Yes	48
3	4	6	2	2	Yes	77
4	5	6	1	4	No	26
5	2	7	3	4	Yes	29
6	3	8	1	4	No	43
7	1	1	10	4	Yes	14
8	4	7	1	4	Yes	56
9	4	5	3	2	Yes	64
10	3	3	6	5	No	6
11	6	6	0	7	No	59
12	7	2	3	6	Yes	44
13	6	3	3	6	Yes	8
14	5	5	2	7	Yes	95
15	4	1	7	4	Yes	0
16	6	5	1	4	No	77
17	5	3	4	6	No	86
18	5	6	1	4	Yes	69
19	7	4	1	2	No	106
Sum:	89	85	54			
Average:	4,7 (SD=1,8)	4,5 (SD=2,0)	2,8 (SD=2,5)			

* FS = formant synthesis,

Average = the arithmetic mean

A.2 Test results and training data for each hashtag

Hashtag:	Amount of PCE* with FS*, Average of EDT* of those participants:	Amount of PCE* without FS*, Average of EDT* of those participants:	Amount of PCE* unmapped, Average of EDT* of those participants:	Total amount of EDT* amongst all participants:	Mean of encounters amongst all participants:
#spring	7, 16.8 (SD = 6.2)	2, 9 (SD=2.8)	10, 5.8 (SD= 5.4)	194	10.2 (SD=7.5)
#joebiden	6, 9.2 (SD=7.5)	11, 13.5 (SD=6.6)	2, 0.5 (SD=0.7)	204	10.7 (SD=7.5)
#influencer	10, 2.7 (SD=1.3)	5, 4.0 (SD=0.7)	4, 0.5 (SD=1.0)	49	2.6 (SD=1.6)
#donaldtrump	7, 6.0 (SD=3.9)	8, 6.0 (SD=4.9)	4, 2.8 (SD=3.1)	101	5.3 (SD=4.2)
#fridaysforfuture	4, 0.3 (SD=0.5)	9, 0.3 (SD=0.7)	6, 0.5 (SD=0.5)	7	0.4 (SD=0.6)
#happybirthday	8, 4.6 (SD=4.3)	6, 7.3 (SD=3.8)	5, 3.8 (SD=5.0)	100	5.3 (SD=4.4)
#facebook	9, 9.2 (SD=7.3)	7, 7.9 (SD=4.1)	3, 12.3 (SD=7.2)	175	9.2 (SD=6.2)
#coffee	7, 0 (SD=0)	6, 0 (SD=0)	6, 0 (SD=0)	0	0 (SD=0)
#crowdfunding	7, 3.0 (SD=3.7)	6, 4.8 (SD=2.3)	6, 1.2 (SD=1.5)	57	3 (SD=3)
#march	8, 2.25 (SD=3.2)	9, 1.2 (SD=1.6)	2, 2.5 (SD= 3.5)	34	1.8 (SD=2.5)
#stockholm	10, 0.3 (SD=0.7)	7, 0.3 (SD=0.5)	2, 0 (SD=0)	5	0.3 (SD=0.6)
#influencermarketing	6, 0.7 (SD=0.8)	9, 0.4 (SD=0.5)	4, 0.3 (SD=0.5)	9	0.5 (SD=0.6)
Total amount of earcons chosen according to set:	89	85	54		

* FS = formant synthesis, PCE = participants choosing earcons, EDT = Encounters during training, Average = the arithmetic mean

A.3 Scatter plot of Total Encounters in relation to Amount of the UM* chosen per person based on MB*

Total Encounters - Amount of UM* chosen per person (based on MB*)

*UM = un-mapped earcons, MB=musical background

A.4 Playback order of earcons according to hashtags during listening test

Order number	Hashtag	A	B	C
1	#spring	UM*	WF*	WOF*
2	#jobbiden	WOF*	UM*	WF*
3	#influencer	WF*	WOF*	UM*
4	#donaldtrump	WOF*	WF*	UM*
5	#fridaysforfuture	UM*	WF*	WOF*
6	#happybirthday	WOF*	UM*	WF*
7	#facebook	WF*	UM*	WOF*
8	#coffee	UM*	WOF*	WF*
9	#crowdfunding	WOF*	WF*	UM*
10	#march	WOF*	UM*	WF*
11	#stockholm	WF*	UM*	WOF*
12	#influencermarketing	UM*	WF*	WOF*

*UM = un-mapped earcon set, WF=earcon set with formant synthesis, WOF=earcon set without formant synthesis

A.5 Frequency spectrum of the #joebiden-carcon with formant synthesis

A.6 Frequency spectrum of the #joebiden-carcon without formant synthesis

